

1 **Xist expression commences prior to sex determination and functions in cell cycle progression.**

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6 The precise moment in development at which Xist expression is described to commence in mammals
7 has been debated. We measured total transcription in the human embryo in the oocyte prior to
8 fertilization, immediately following fertilization (1-cell), at the 2-cell stage, at the 4-cell stage, at the 8-cell
9 stage and in cells of blastocyst derived from the inner cell mass to determine the authentic onset of Xist
10 expression in the human embryo. While high level Xist expression did not commence until the 8-cell
11 stage leading into the gastrulation and pre-implantation embryo development, a spike of Xist expression
12 occurred at the 1-cell stage and was completed by the 2-cell stage, suggesting that Xist activation
13 following fertilization functioned in first cell division of the embryo following fertilization. Xist activation
14 was concomitant with CDK6 activation suggesting Xist induction supported progression of the cell cycle
15 in early embryogenesis. The data illustrate Xist expression at a much earlier developmental stage than
16 previously understood. Xist expression commences and appears functional prior to sex determination.
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